

Non-isothermal degradation and kinetic parameters of bidentate Schiff base complexes

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Present report discusses some aspects of non-isothermal kinetic studies of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes of bidentate Schiff base derived from dehydroacetic acid and *p*-toluidine.

In 1958, Freeman and Carroll published their methods for kinetic analysis of thermoanalytical data¹. Since then various methods have been put forward for estimation of kinetic parameters and they are methods of Coats-Redfern², Dharwadkar-Kharkhanawala³, Asako Doyle⁴, Fuoss *et al.*⁵ and Horowitz-Metzger⁶. These methods have been applied depending upon their needs and conditions for kinetic analysis of thermal decomposition of the solid substances^{7,8}. Thermal decomposition of many coordination compounds of transition metals by Horowitz-Metzger method have been reported^{8,9}. Horowitz-Metzger method gives reasonably good results as compared to other methods which are time-consuming. Therefore, Horowitz-Metzger method has been used for finding the kinetic parameters of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes of Schiff base derived from dehydroacetic acid and *p*-toluidine in the present communication.

The equation used for calculation of kinetic parameters by Horowitz-Metzger method is

$$\log(\log W_c/W_r) = E_a \theta / 2.3 RT_m^2 - \log 2.3$$

where, E_a is the activation energy, $W_r = W_c - W$ (W_c = weight-loss at completion of reaction, and W = total weight-loss up to time t), R is the gas constant, T the absolute temperature, T_m the peak temperature, such that $T_m = W_i/W_0 = 1/E_a$; $\theta = T - T_m$.

An apparent activation entropy can be calculated using the equation,

$$(\Delta S) = 2.303 R \log Zh/kT$$

where, Z is the frequency factor, h the Planck constant, and k the Boltzmann constant.

Results and Discussion

Thermal studies of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes :

Thermogravimetric studies indicate that the metal complexes are thermally quite stable. Decomposition of all the complexes started at relatively higher temperatures and was complete above 650° and the weights of the residues correspond to the formation of metal oxides. The thermogravimetric curve of the Cu^{II} complex shows a peak at 314.6° which indicates decomposition temperature of the complex. The endothermic peak observed in DTA curve around 270.9° followed by two broad exothermic peaks at 439.9 and 589.7° may be due to decomposition of organic ligand and subsequent slow oxidation¹⁰.

The thermogram of the Ni^{II} complex reveals that the metal chelate follows single step decomposition with a single exothermic peak at 343.5°. The weight-loss observed in the thermogravimetric curve of the Co^{II} complex at 40–105 and 110–220° could be correlated with loss of water of crystallization and the removal of coordinated water respectively¹¹. The weight-loss at 110.5° supported by a broad exothermic peak in DTA curve is the characteristic of loss of one molecule of lattice water¹². The second step encountered at 240° corresponds to initiation of breaking of organic constituent of the complex. The decomposition at 337° in TG curve is supported by two endothermic peaks at 312 and 486° in DTA curve.

In TG curve of the Fe^{III} complex, the peak at 274° may be the decomposition temperature of organic matter and that at 328° indicates the decomposition temperature of the complex. An exothermic peak at 87.9° in the DTA curve corresponds to loss of one molecule of water of crystallization. The TG curve of the Mn^{II} complex exhibits a weight-loss at 256.9° attributable to decomposition of the chelate. The organic moiety completely decomposes at 231–289° which is ascertained by similar peaks in DTA curve. The exothermic peak at 61° in DTA curve indicates the presence of lattice water or water of crystallization.

Thermal decomposition and kinetic parameters of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} complexes :

The non-isothermal kinetic parameters of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} with Schiff base DHA-4-methylphenylaniil (L₁) have been calculated from the thermograms. The log (log W_c/W_r) vs θ curves are constructed on the basis of thermogravimetric data for all the five complexes. The decomposition reaction for the loss of Schiff base moiety from the complex was subjected to non-isothermal kinetic studies at a uniform heating rate of 10°/min. The weighted least-squares method was used for obtaining best-fit linear plots by applying the data of HM method and the kinetic parameters were calculated. The values of slope, intercept and energy of activation were obtained from the plots.

The thermograms of the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes show one stage thermal decomposition with a single peak at 314.6 and 343.5°, respectively. The thermograms of the Co^{II}, Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} complexes show more than one stage of decomposition. The higher values of activation energy (Table 1) of the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes show higher stability than the Co^{II}, Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} complexes. In the present studies, the numerical values of activation energy, frequency factor and entropy of activation indicate about smoothness of the feasibility and reaction rate of the initial reactants and intermolecular stage compounds.

Table 1. Thermal kinetic parameters of the complexes on the basis of Horowitz-Metzger (H-M) method

Compd.	Decomp. stage temp. (K)	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔF kJ mol ⁻¹	Z s ⁻¹
L ₁ -Cu ^{II} (1)	I/587	96.59	197.00	110.10	623
L ₁ -Ni ^{II} (2)	I/616.5	63.42	162.66	75.48	317
L ₁ -Co ^{II} (3)	I/513.4	22.22	197.03	123.33	549
	II/610.4	15.70	199.74	137.54	470
	III/824	14.31	199.24	137.54	653
L ₁ -Mn ^{II} (4)	I/529.9	63.06	203.61	174.43	264
	II/722	30.45	204.31	153.24	167
L ₁ -Fe ^{III} (5)	I/547	24.74	205.49	133.63	204
	II/601	38.93	209.74	190.41	168

The negative values for entropy of activation indicate that the activated complexes have more ordered or more rigid structure than the reactants or intermediate and the reactions are slower than normal¹³ which is further supported by low Z values. The order of thermal stability of compounds is 2 > 1 > 5 > 4 > 3 (on the basis of first decomposition state) and 4 > 3 > 5 (on the basis of second decomposition state). The order of the stability of compounds on the basis of the values of activation energy is 1 > 2 > 4 > 5 > 3 (for first stage) and 5 > 4 > 3 (for second stage).

On application of the above mentioned method on the thermogravimetric traces of these complexes, E_a , Z , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔF values were obtained for the thermal decomposition reactions (Table 1). The E_a values are sufficiently high while ΔS^\ddagger values are negative. These values are comparable with other observations^{8,9}.

Experimental

The Schiff base (ligand) was synthesized by adding an ethanolic solution of the appropriate amine (*p*-toluidine) to an ethanolic solution of lactone (dehydroacetic acid) in 1 : 1 molar ratio and refluxing the resulting mixture for 4–6 h. The white product was crystallized from ethanol. Purity of the compound was checked by TLC.

The metal complexes were synthesized by adding a methanolic solution of the appropriate metal salt MCl₂·xH₂O (0.01 mol) to a methanolic solution of the Schiff base (DHA-*p*-toluidine; 0.02 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. To the cold solution, 10% alcoholic ammonia solution was added dropwise till the precipitate was formed. The complexes of different metals were precipitated at different pHs. The complexes were filtered in hot condition, washed with hot methanol followed by petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°), and dried under reduced pressure over anhyd. CaCl₂ in a desiccator.

The thermogravimetric analysis and differential thermal analysis were been carried out at RSIC, Chennai, at a heating rate 10° per min from room temperature to 1000° in nitrogen atmosphere.

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Note

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